

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The processing/structure/property relationships of a model crystalline thermoplastic composite was investigated. Deformation and failure modes of polypropylene, rubber-modified PP, and fiber-reinforced PP were studied as a function of material variables and testing conditions. Mechanical properties of hybrid composites containing combined thermoplastic-thermoset matrices were also examined.

INTRODUCTION

Several advantages have been recognized for the thermoplastic over the thermoset resins in composite applications. These include a short molding cycle, easy fabrication, indefinite prepreg shelf life, convenient storage conditions, excellent chemical and corrosion resistance, thermal stability, post-molding reformability, good repairability and so forth [1]. Most recent developments include semicrystalline polyetheretherketone (PEEK) [2], polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) [3], and many others. Processing of these materials usually involves relatively high temperatures, and special tools are often required. Polypropylene (PP) is readily crystallizable, easy to process (high temperature not required), and a wide range of crystallinities and crystal dimensions can be obtained with PP [4,5]. In the present investigation, PP was chosen as a model matrix material for composites to study the effects of E-glass fiber reinforcement and impact modifiers on the structure and properties of crystalline polymers. In addition, this investigation seeks to determine if the impact and fracture properties of a brittle epoxy-fiber composite can be improved with the addition of varying amounts of PPS-based thermoplastic composite layers (hybridization).

EXPERIMENTAL

A series of PP-rubber blends with rubber content ranging from 0% to 30% were prepared. By means of a sheet-extrusion process, PP and SBR were blended into thin sheets. Uniaxial glass fabric layers interleaved with PP-rubber sheets and epoxy/PPS fiber prepreps were used to prepare single- and hybrid-matrix composites, respectively, by compression molding. Hybrid-matrix specimens are listed in Table 1. Two types of sample geometries were used:

Table 1. PPS/Epoxy Hybrid Composites

Pc(50)/Ec(50)...	50% PPS-graphite/50% epoxy-graphite (Pc Ec Pc Ec) _s
Pg(50)/Ec(50)...	50% PPS-glass/50% epoxy-graphite (Pg Ec Pg Ec) _s
Pc(100).....	100% PPS-graphite
Pg(100).....	100% PPS-glass
Ec(100).....	100% epoxy-graphite

thin plate of 10.16 x 10.16 cm and thick rectangular bars of 13.26 x 1.03 cm. The following processing conditions were chosen for the epoxy/PPS hybrid composites: 250 F (i.e. the temperature specified for epoxy prepreg) and 95 psi for 1 hour, then 250 F and contact pressure for 30 minutes (post cure).

The impact properties were measured by using a Dynatup 730 instrumented falling-weight impact tester. Both force-deflection and absorbed energy-deflection traces were recorded. The thin plate samples were used for impact penetration test and thick rectangular bar samples for Charpy-type impact and post-impact 3-point bending tests. The microstructure of the samples was studied by using a Jeol scanning electron microscope (JSM 840 SEM). PP spherulite morphology around both glass fibers and rubber particles was also studied by using polarized light microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Morphology and Crystallinity of Rubber or Fiber Modified PP

Microscopy study indicates that addition of an impact modifier such as SBR results in a less regular spherulite texture with less sharp spherulite boundaries. However, the size of the spherulite is not changed appreciably by the incorporation of the rubbery phase. The SEM micrographs (will be shown at the meeting) demonstrate that the rubber particles are randomly distributed in the PP matrix. Analysis of the DSC data suggests that the degree of crystallinity of the PP matrix in the PP-rubber blends do not vary as the rubbery phase is added. This implies that very little mixing (compatibility) at the molecular level exists in the solid state and very little interfacial adhesion is anticipated between the rubbery phase and PP matrix.

Randomly oriented spherulites appear to be the dominant morphology in the vicinity of glass fibers incorporated in the PP matrix. Because the fiber volume fraction of the fiber composite materials is high, the spherulites grown at the interstices within fiber bundles have limited dimensions. In the resin-rich zones in a composite, the spherulites are relatively large in size. Since PP is a highly crystalline polymer and is known to undergo pronounced shrinkage upon crystallization, small voids tend to form in these fiber deficient areas. In order to avoid the unwanted inter-spherulitic growth of cracks, resin-rich areas in a composite should be reduced or eliminated.

2. Impact Response of The Unnotched Charpy Bars

All the impact-loaded bars show certain extent of compressive damage on the top surface due to impactor-material interaction. This compressive failure mode is characterized by the presence of the transverse cracks through the uppermost few laminas, accompanied by a few short-range longitudinal delamination cracks. In most samples, the bottom few layers also fail by a combination of transverse tensile cracking (along the thickness direction) and some associated delamination. The tensile cracking involves small extent of fiber breakage and matrix cracking. In addition, the inner layers usually also exhibit longer-range delamination, with the delamination cracks possibly extended to one or both ends. In general, the thickness-direction cracks are fiber-dominated while the delamination interface- and matrix-dominated. For PP matrix composites, since PP resin is capable of undergoing a great extent of plastic deformation, fabric layers are shifted relative to each other in response to the impact loading. This matrix-controlled plastic deformation phenomenon, in conjunction with delamination, acts to dissipate the great majority of impact energy.

Fig.1 Impact Response of Charpy Bars

Sample Pg(100), containing 100% PPS/Glass, shows a moderate level of compressive damage and delamination, plus a small degree of tensile fracture. The amount of impact energy absorbed (13.9 J) is moderate. Sample Pc(100), containing 100% PPS/Carbon, usually shows a "cut-type" through-the-thickness crack, which propagates in a very brittle fashion without much delamination. As a result, the energy absorbed in this sample is relatively low (11.8 J). Occasionally, Pc(100) specimen may respond to the impact loading by a rapid, clean delamination accompanied by only a small degree of compressive damage, again leading to a small energy absorption value. The unnotched Charpy bars of Ec(100) dissipate a surprisingly high amount of impact energy (19.4 J) by forming a through-the-thickness crack, in conjunction with moderately extensive delamination (Fig.1). A compressive damage plus a large number of small-scale delamination cracks serve to absorb a great deal of energy (16.7 J) in Sample Pg(50)/Ec(50). This high extent of delamination is apparently induced by the alternating stacking sequence of different laminas (hybridization). Nevertheless, the specimens of Pc(50)/Ec(50) often fail by one rapid and clean interlaminar separation that does not allow for delamination cracks to occur in other interfaces. Consequently, very little energy (8.83 J) is absorbed in this sample. This easy separation is most likely caused by poor bonding between PPS-graphite and epoxy-graphite laminas.

Fig.2 Effect of Test Temperature on Impact Response

3. Effect of Test Temperature on Impact Response

The impact response of PP-resin and PP-fiber composites as a function of test temperature is shown in Fig. 2. At relatively low temperature ($T < 25$ C), the PP resin is brittle and tends to rupture in a brittle mode. However, when the test temperature is raised, the improved material flexibility facilitates a greater flexural deformation of the test bar, leading to an increased amount of total energy dissipated. At still

higher temperatures ($>50^{\circ}\text{C}$), the flexural deformation is so great that the specimen simply slides through between the two supporting points of the test fixture without deforming to its full capacity, thereby giving falsely low impact energy

The yield strength of PP generally decreases with increasing test temperature. The degree of fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion in the PP-matrix composites is provided for by the crystallization shrinkage of PP matrix and the differential thermal contraction between PP and glass fibers. The residual thermal stresses are expected to decrease at a higher test temperature, making it easier for delamination to occur. Delamination does not appear to require a high external stress and does not dissipate a large amount of impact energy when the test temperatures are high (Fig.2). Contrarily, when the test temperatures are too low ($< -20^{\circ}\text{C}$), both the matrix strength and interface bond are so strong that the brittle failure prevails. Both delamination and tension cracks propagate to a limited extent, thereby restricting the energy absorbing capability of the composite specimen.

4. Impact Response of The Thin Plate Samples

Physical blending of PP with SBR rubber appears to slightly increase the maximum load experienced by the composite plates. The primary mode of failure in these plates appears to be penetration. Since the projectile penetration of a composite laminate is a fiber-dominated phenomenon, matrix modifications alone in PP composites would not likely improve the impact resistance of fiber composites.

Fig. 3. Representative E-t Curve for Impact Response of Thin Plate Sample.

For the PPS/epoxy composites samples, following the front-face indentation that involves the pushing of a small disc of material on the first few lamina layers, the subsequent perforation does not occur around the perimeter of the impactor. Instead, the fiber bundles are broken at arbitrary locations inside the perimeter. This indicates the ductile nature of this thermoplastic matrix. Further, the interfacial bonding between the fibers and the PPS matrix is relatively poor. Figure 3 compares the representative E-t curves. As expected, Sample $\text{Ec}(100)$ has the lowest energy while Sample $\text{Pg}(100)$ exhibits the highest energy level. Adding certain amount of PPS-glass or PPS-graphite prepreps can improve the total energy absorbed by the epoxy-graphite composites.

The SEM micrgraphs of the impact fracture surfaces within sample $\text{Pc}(50)/\text{Ec}(50)$ (will be shown at the meeting) demonstrate that epoxy-graphite layers have undergone a brittle failure mode similar to Sample $\text{Ec}(100)$. A rather clean break can be seen with little fiber pullout or fiber-matrix debonding as present in Samples $\text{Pc}(100)$ and $\text{Pg}(100)$. This implies that epoxy

bonds to the fibers much better than PPS bonds to either the glass or graphite fibers. The brittleness of a graphite-epoxy composite is caused by both epoxy and fibers, lacking the ability to undergo plastic deformation. Also, the fiber-matrix bonding is too good to allow the energy-absorbing mechanisms such as interfacial debonding and fiber pull-out to operate to any significant extent. As a consequence, the crack propagated in a catastrophic manner.

5. Post-Impact Three-Point Bending Tests

Examination of low-energy impacted samples prior to three point bending shows that, for $E_c(100)$ and $P_g(100)$, no damage could be detected. However, for $P_c(50)/E_c(50)$, $P_g(50)/E_c(50)$, and $P_c(100)$, delamination is observed and the greater the number of impacts the more severe the impact damage. For these samples, the load and stiffness drop off considerably after the first or second impacts and the residual strength of these two samples decreases with increasing impact number. Visual inspection of the samples after three point bending showed large amounts of interply delamination within many different layers of each sample. On the contrary, Sample $E_c(100)$ and $P_g(100)$ show little sign of loss of residual strength even after 8 repeated impacts. Nevertheless, $E_c(100)$ was fractured completely into two pieces during three point bending.

6. Toughened PPs and Their Fiber Composites

Adding a small amount of SBR has been found to be effective in toughening the PP neat resin. However, the toughening effects of the rubbery phase are gradually nullified when the rubber content exceeds 20%. This is most likely caused by the poor distribution of rubber particles and the large dimensions of these particles, which are not efficient in promoting and controlling the crazing and shear yielding processes [6]. In the case of fiber-PP composites, blending the matrix resin with a rubbery phase does not prove to be beneficial. Both P_m and E_t (unnotched Charpy) of a composite, when containing more than 15% rubber in the matrix, are inferior to those of a control fiber composite without rubber. Similar results were obtained when the notched Charpy impact tests were performed. In general, a higher rubber content in the resin matrix leads to an inferior impact performance of fiber composites (Fig.4). Short beam shear tests indicate that the ILSS has been reduced by incorporation of rubber in the matrix. This implies that the rubbery phase has decreased the matrix yield strength and perhaps the interfacial bonding as well. This action has made it easier to have interlaminar separation associated with transverse buckling, which is the primary mode of failure in this group of composites.

Fig.4 Charpy Impact Response as a Function of wt% SBR in PP.

Fig. 5. Relationship Between Impact Responses of Neat Resin and Composites.

Figure 5 shows the total energy absorbed by the composite is seen to be inversely related to the matrix toughness. However, in most of other cases, correlation cannot be found. These diagrams reconfirm our speculation that an improvement in matrix toughness does not necessarily result in an enhanced toughness of composite. The fact that no evidence of crazing could be found between fibers and within fiber bundles could suggest shear stress fields prevailing in these physically restricted zones. With a reduced amount of resin in these zones, the degree of plastic deformation in resin would be limited. Further, deformation and microfailure mechanisms other than matrix yielding (e.g. interfacial debonding, fiber pull-out, and some fiber breakage) may predominate. Therefore, toughening a ductile matrix polymer may not necessarily result in an improved toughness of the fiber composites.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Delamination has been found to be the dominant failure mode in PP-fiber composite subjected to low-velocity impact. The maximum load tolerated by the laminates just prior to delamination appears to be controlled by the resin yield strength and the fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion.
2. The limited interstitial space within and between fiber bundles acts to restrict the growth of plastic deformation modes such as crazing and shear banding. Also, the high shear stress field associated with delamination is not expected to be in favor of crazing. Therefore, a much lesser degree of stress whitening phenomenon was observed in glass fiber reinforced rubber-modified PP.
3. Rubber modifications of PP matrix did not lead to an improvement in impact resistance of fiber composite.
4. Adding thermoplastic PPS-fiber laminas was found effective in improving the energy absorption capability of brittle epoxy composites.
5. The interply bond between the hybrid matrix samples, Pc(50)/Ec(50) and Pg(50)/Ec(50), is not sufficiently strong, resulting in excessive delamination for stress relaxation and energy dissipation upon impact.
6. The bonding between the epoxy matrix and graphite fiber samples is better than the bonding between the PPS matrix and either of the glass or graphite fibers. Therefore, Sample Ec proved to be the best overall performer with the most consistent and highest maximum load.

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